

Data Pitch

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D6.2 Dissemination, engagement, communication strategy

Coordinator: Helen Desmond

**With contributions from: Orsola De Marco, Heidi
Lindvall**

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Abstract

This document sets out the dissemination, engagement and communications strategy for the Data Pitch project. It addresses the objectives for the project, the target audiences, messages channels and tactics for effective communication.

Executive summary

This document presents the overall dissemination, engagement and communication strategy for the Data Pitch project. The work is being led by the Data Pitch communications team, but the whole consortium plays a role in deploying it.

The main elements of this project's dissemination, engagement and communication strategy are:

- **Utilising the full reach of the Data Pitch consortium networks**
- **Community building**
- **Employing a multi-channel approach**
- **Strategic media engagement**
- **Collaboration with other related (EU) projects**

We are using crafted messaging targeting the key audience groups: startups, organisations with data, and other interested parties. These messages focus on the benefits of joining the Data Pitch ecosystem for each group, including clear calls to action. We are targeting these audiences using channels they already use, or new channels, such as the Data Pitch website, which offer them clear information and advice, and engaging content.

We are taking a coordinated approach to reaching out to stakeholder networks, capitalising on the relationships existing within the consortium across Europe.

Events form an important part in spreading the word about Data Pitch and meeting our target audiences face to face. We are cataloging events that hold value for Data Pitch, assessing them based on their reach, audience and strategic value. In this way we are ensuring face to face engagement across Europe at top priority events.

We are creating engaging, audience focused content which can be adapted for use across a range of channels, from blogs, to press releases to the website. We are using this content to build a Data Pitch community both online and offline - encouraging conversation and engagement.

This strategy is a flexible plan which will allow the Data Pitch team to adapt to future developments, especially the lessons learned from the first months of the project and its initial activities.

Introduction

This report sets out the dissemination, engagement and communications strategy for how the Data Pitch communications team, with the support of the wider Data Pitch consortium, is effectively reaching the project's target audiences with compelling messages and calls to action, securing their involvement in the project.

A strong dissemination, engagement and communications plan is essential for any project and needs to be integral to the processes and culture. While the communications team at the ODI is leading the work in this document, all the consortium partners are contributing to ensure that Data Pitch is communicated consistently and widely. In particular Data Pitch is making use of the extensive reach of the European stakeholder networks of the consortium.

The strategy below sets out how each of the target audiences for the campaign is being reached using messages which clearly set out the benefits of getting involved in the project, using relevant and well respected channels.

Objectives

Whilst Data Pitch has overarching project objectives, the following goals relate specifically to the work of the communications team and have been developed to chime with the target metrics set out in the initial grant agreement. See Annex 1 [here](#).

- To utilise the full range of communications channels available to ensure that Data Pitch reaches as many of its target audiences as possible, informing them of Data Pitch's business and societal benefits, and making it clear how they can get involved.
- To raise awareness of, and drive applications to the calls to action amongst key target groups, including the consultation to define the Data Pitch challenges and the open calls for startups.
- To promote Data Pitch successes and case studies demonstrating the project's value and impact, including innovative challenge solutions, and concepts.
- To showcase the high-potential companies accepted onto the programme, including promoting new cohorts, profiling startups.
- To showcase of the impact of data-driven innovation for the public and private sector organisations.
- To build an active Data Pitch community of businesses, researchers, investors and commentators, who are active participants in the established ecosystem.

Audiences

There are a number of audiences for the Data Pitch project. We are targeting each group with the right messages, at the right time, using the most appropriate channel.

Primary audiences

- **Private and public-sector businesses and organisations that have data** and are interested in working with Data Pitch to set challenges that startups and SMEs can develop solutions for.
- **Startup businesses and SMEs** who work with data and are interested in applying to be part of the accelerator programme.
- **Other individuals and organisations** who can support the Data Pitch startups e.g., mentors, advisors, technology suppliers and service providers.

There are secondary audiences who are part of the wider Data Pitch ecosystem

- **Angel investors and VC's** who are looking for innovative, data-driven startups to network, mentor or invest in.
- **Other accelerator programmes** who want to partner with Data Pitch.
- **SME and enterprise networks** with extensive startup communities who can support outreach activities.
- **Sector specific member organisations, institutions and media outlets** that are relevant to the Data Pitch challenges.
- **Tech, data and innovation commentators** and bloggers, including journalists.

Key messages and calls to action

Below is a narrative which describes Data Pitch and is used as the default language when talking about the project. Below the narrative are key messages by audience - these take into account the motivations and barriers for each group. Ultimately these key messages answer the question: '*Data Pitch: what's in it for me?*'.

The Data Pitch Narrative

Data Pitch is a European *data innovation ecosystem* bringing together data owners and Big Data technology providers, with startups and SMEs with fresh ideas for data-driven products and services.

Messages for data providers

- Become a Data Pitch data provider and let our startups address some of your top business and sector challenges. Find out more and contact us via our website: www.datapitch.eu/about-us/data-providers/.
- Data Pitch is for organisations who want to explore an open innovation approach with data. We offer bespoke support: from data sharing technology, to the legal aspects of data use and engagement with startups.
- Data Pitch supports organisations running their own innovation programmes or collaborating with startups and SMEs to build data services.
- Join Data Pitch to:
 - Access skilled startups who can build solutions to your challenges
 - Bring fresh ideas into your organisation quickly with low risk and low cost
 - Utilise Data Pitch's data sharing know-how, plus its legal expertise and its experience working with startups
 - Learn more about your data and how it can be used with other data
 - Forge a relationship with an innovation partner
 - Find a company you may want to invest in

For more detailed messaging go to: www.datapitch.eu/about-us/data-providers/.

Messages for startups

- Data Pitch offers talented, data-driven startups who are accepted onto the accelerator equity free funding of up to €100k, and the opportunity to find solutions to important industry and societal challenges.
- Data Pitch is for startups and SMEs who:
 - Want to create products and services with data
 - Want to work alongside established businesses and corporates
 - Are registered in an EU country or an Horizon 2020 associated country. See list in [annex 4](#)
- **Join Data Pitch to:**
 - Receive equity free funding of up to €100k
 - Build new solutions to challenges that affect businesses and the public with data
 - Get early-stage access to the market by collaborating with private and public sector organisations and helping them innovate
 - Demonstrate your data expertise to potential clients and investors
 - Be part of an ecosystem where you can share ideas and collaborate with other startups
 - Benefit from mentoring, office space, networking opportunities, communications support and other business resources
 - Apply for a place on the Data Pitch accelerator from 1st July, go to: www.datapitch.eu/apply/

For more detailed messaging go to: www.datapitch.eu/about-us/start-up/.

Messages for those interested in supporting Data Pitch

- Data Pitch is bringing together a wide range of data owners, businesses of all sizes, data and technology experts, platform providers, investors, accelerator programmes and more.
- We want you to be part of this new European data 'ecosystem' which will enable and support data innovation.
- Get involved in Data Pitch by:
 - Mentoring
 - Providing expertise in data and business growth
 - Technology provision
 - Funding vibrant startups and SMEs

Strategic engagement approach

There are four key aspects to the strategic engagement approach the Data Pitch team is taking to communicate with target audiences in the most effective, efficient way:

1. Utilising the full reach of the Data Pitch consortium networks

The four Data Pitch consortium partners each have their own extensive networks of customers, members, associates, research partners, and businesses which stretch across Europe. The Data Pitch Communications team is employing a hub and spoke model in order to effectively engage and make best use of each of these consortium networks. This involves:

- The core communications team at the ODI developing tools, resources and materials which can be adapted and customised by the consortium members for their own needs and those of their network members. For example:
 - The development of visual, branded Twitter cards which can be easily customised into local languages.
 - Standard text which can be translated and used to email stakeholder networks
 - Press notices with adequate time given for translation
- A **virtual** Data Pitch communications team including representatives from each of the consortium partner communications teams who are able to collate local stakeholder lists and coordinate outreach to those networks using the centrally developed tools and materials.
- The core communications team at the ODI ensuring effective lines of communication between the virtual team via regular conference calls and emails.

2. Community building

We are building a community of interested individuals and organisations, via online and offline channels who we will keep engaged throughout the life of the project. We are doing this via:

- Developing our following on Twitter and Facebook with news about the project, including key milestones, attendance at expos, hackathons and industry events, calls to action, Data Pitch news stories and blogs, media coverage and relevant industry news.
- Encouraging people to sign up for the Data Pitch newsletter on the website. We are developing a newsletter around key milestones and calls to action and encouraging community members to put forward their own blog ideas.

- Encouraging the community to come along to events, hackathons and meetups where Data Pitch representatives are present via Twitter and Facebook.

3. A multi channel approach

We use the full range of communications and marketing channels available to us to communicate with target audiences in a way which suits them. The focus is on 'going to them' rather than expecting them to 'come to us'. This multi-channel approach includes channels which are 'owned' by Data Pitch, such as the website, or our newsletter; ones that are owned by others, such as industry events, or media outlets; and community/social channels such as Twitter and Facebook. See [the 'Channel Strategy' section below](#) for more on the topic.

4. Strategic media outreach

The Data Pitch Communications team are developing press releases around key moments and calls to action in the project, for example: the official launch of Data Pitch on April 10th 2017, and the launch of the Open Call on the 1st July. These press releases are being distributed across Europe by working closely with the comms teams from the consortium and maximising existing media contacts and trusted journalist relationships. We are targeting SME, startup, business, investment and tech media as appropriate.

5. Close collaboration with other related (EU) projects

We are working closely with other European and EC funded projects, these include [EU BusinessGraph](#) and 15 other projects. Data Pitch is part of the Big Data Value Public Private Partnership.

Channel strategy

We are reaching our key audiences using a range of relevant and effective channels. Some of these channels are Data Pitch's own channels, and some external.

Data Pitch channels and uses

1. The website

[The Data Pitch website](https://datapitch.eu)¹ is the 'home' for all public facing information, notifications, resources, blogs, news stories and forthcoming opportunities for engagement. The website is managed by the core Data Pitch communications team and updated on a weekly basis. It aggregates all dissemination, engagement and communication activities of Data Pitch into one conclusive online presence.

On the website, interested parties can:

- Find out how Data Pitch can benefit them, whether they are a startup, a data provider, or simply an interested party
- Get in touch with the Data Pitch team
- Find the latest news from Data Pitch
- Read blogs from the Data Pitch team and community
- Follow our social media accounts
- Subscribe to the mailing list in order to get the latest news about Data Pitch project
- Apply for a place on the accelerator and respond to Data Pitch surveys
- See which companies have been accepted onto Data Pitch and read case studies about them

¹ <https://datapitch.eu>

- View the Data Pitch deliverables
- View the Data Pitch resources and tools
- View the webinars such as startup applications, online training etc.
- View a list of mentors in the programme
- View a list of partners from the wider Data Pitch network

2. Newsletter

From July 2017 the Data Pitch communications team will create a newsletter around key calls to action and new information relevant to the Data Pitch community. The newsletter will include:

- a. Calls to action, driving people to the web site
- b. Blogs from the community and the Data Pitch team
- c. News items
- d. Startup profiles
- e. Number of datasets published
- f. Short vlogs from companies accepted onto the programme

3. Social Media - Twitter, Facebook

We have developed the following social media channels for Data Pitch, they play a key role in building an online, Europe-wide community around Data Pitch:

- Twitter: @DataPitchEU²
- Facebook: Data Pitch³

We have also created a Buffer account to schedule social media posts and created social media cards to make Tweets etc more visually appealing.

We will use these social media channels to:

1. Direct traffic to various pages of the Data Pitch website at relevant times, for example:
 - To submit a challenge idea
 - To apply to the call for a position in the programme
 - To read new blogs and news stories
 - To find out more about what Data Pitch can do for the different stakeholders

Example Tweet:

² <https://twitter.com/DataPitchEU>

³ <https://www.facebook.com/Data-Pitch-402275080131867/>

2. Flag media coverage which either focuses on or features Data Pitch (ie, coverage we have directly generated from our media work)

You Retweeted

 Data Pitch @DataPitchEU · Apr 11

ICYMI here's our exclusive piece with TechCrunch announcing the launch of Data Pitch!

Europe funds another data accelerator to get startups tackling...
A new European Commission-funded startup accelerator, Data Pitch, is being launched today with the aim of connecting established businesse...
techcrunch.com

3. Point to other relevant 'curated' online content, for example:

- Interesting news stories, articles and opinion pieces about open innovation, startups, data, European trading success
- Other companies, programmes and accelerators innovating with data.

You Retweeted

 The Next Web Europe @TheNextWebEU · May 22

Europe isn't the new Silicon Valley. It's better

Europe isn't the new Silicon Valley. It's better
European startups have several key advantages over their American counterparts.
thenextweb.com

4. To engage in conversation with the extended Data Pitch community and answer their queries.

Our social media strategy will also:

- Raise awareness of the 'webinars' and how startups can get involved
- Promote our startups and projects to a wider audience - highlighting successful growth or news to prospective investors and partners
- Share our own events and those of interest to the community
- Celebrate milestones for Data Pitch

4. Consortium partner channels (Dawex, Beta-i, ODI, University of Southampton)

- Partner websites - cross posting of new stories and calls to action
- Partner newsletters - notifying networks of the Data Pitch programme and opportunities to get involved around calls to action
- Social Media - Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn - retweeting of Data Pitch tweets, and posting their own tweets, linking to the Data Pitch website and social channels

5. Wider stakeholder channels

This includes data providers, other accelerator programmes, Twitter followers and other interested organisations.

- Websites
- Newsletters
- Social media

Presence at events

Attending events is a crucial channel for Data Pitch consortium members to meet stakeholders face to face, to encourage them to become part of the Data Pitch community and to build longer term working relationships. Some of the events already attended by the Data Pitch team can be seen in [Annex 2](#).

The types of events below are being researched, recorded and assessed for suitability and relevance on a specific Data Pitch events planner which is reviewed by the whole consortium on a weekly basis.

- Exhibitions - Data Pitch is attending a range of tech, innovation and data events, chosen based on their reach and sector focus and ability to help Data Pitch achieve its objectives: to partner with forward thinking data providers, to drive the best applications to the accelerator, and to create a Europe-wide innovation eco-system. Data Pitch representatives will attend with a branded stand, flyers, stickers and other merchandise.
- Hackathons - Data Pitch is taking part in a range of sector technology and business hackathons in order to develop and refine the industry challenges for the open call and encourage startups to apply for a place on the accelerator. Similarly to the exhibitions, these will be chosen according to their industry focus, target audience and reach.
- Meet-ups - These are regular, community focused events which Data Pitch will attend depending on the need to reach particular parts of the tech/data ecosystems.

Any member of the consortium presenting at an event uses the designed Data Pitch Powerpoint

presentation for consistency of look and message.

All members of the consortium flag their participation on Twitter and on participation-lists for the event (for example Lanyard, Meetup).

Pre-event checklist for consortium members:

- Announce participation on Data Pitch channels
- Contact high priority stakeholders
- Schedule meetings

During an event consortium members:

- Meet with relevant people
- Tweet/blog from the conference
- Deliver presentations etc

Immediately after an event the following actions are taken:

- Tweet the same or next day (“great conference #hashtagconf ...”)
- Write a brief blog post with short summary, maybe linking to external blog post, reviews, videos within a few days. See example of such a blog [here](#).
- Update Data Pitch stakeholder list
- If needed follow up with those persons (add on Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.)
- Invite them to join, participate, like Tweets etc.

Working with the media

Types of media outlets:

1. Online media outlets - the Data Pitch comms team works with these to place news articles, byline articles, blogs, features and profiles. These include Europe-wide outlets such as TechCrunch and the The Next Web.
2. Print outlets - these include national newspapers, and hardcopy magazines such as Wired.
3. Radio and broadcast outlets - interview opportunities with senior members of the team around specific news stories and calls to action. These include BBC Radio 4, and World Service.

The Data Pitch communications team seeks **editorial media coverage** - this is coverage gained through presenting compelling news stories, byline articles, and opinion pieces to journalists, capitalising on the media relationships of the team. This is **not** paid-for editorial coverage and therefore it cannot be guaranteed. Sometimes, particularly around big Data Pitch announcements such as the Open Call, press releases will be the best way to consistently convey a ‘story’ to the media. But the Data Pitch comms teams will usually work closely with targeted news outlets to give them the information they need on a case by case basis, so they can write a piece tailored to their audience.

Data Pitch press releases include all/some the following elements:

- A strong and clear call to action
- Compelling business stats
- Case studies of successful startups who are taking part in the accelerator
- Quote from a the Data Pitch team leader, data provider, startup and/or an authoritative voices in the online startup/business/data community
- Some of the datasets that will be available to experiment and innovate with on the programme, and the organisations providing them

- Explanation of the application process, the webinars and business benefits
- Keys dates in the Data Pitch calendar for startups

Examples of Data Pitch news ‘hooks’ and stories:

- The public facing launch of the programme
- The launch of the Open Call
- Announcement of new cohorts of startups
- Impact stories from startups on how their solution is ‘shifting the dial’ in a specific sector or business

In addition to news stories, the Data Pitch Communications will also be seeking to place:

- Blogs and opinion pieces from the Data Pitch team about pertinent issues for startups and data providers. To note, these are issues-focused articles that show Data Pitch understands the challenges and opportunities for businesses, their purpose is not to ‘sell’ Data Pitch but to position its senior representatives as ‘thought leaders’.
- Company profiles of the startups
- Features and one-off interviews

Website content strategy

The Data Pitch website is continually refreshed with new content. The Data Pitch communications team updates it as soon as new material is approved and ready to post. This includes:

- **News stories** about the latest developments at Data Pitch - for example, the outcomes of a successful hackathon, new cohorts being announced, or impact stories from the startups

- **Calls to action** directing users to methods of engagement and clearly explaining ‘what’s in it for them’. This includes Data Pitch surveys, application forms, etc
- **Blogs** from both Data Pitch team members and the wider Data Pitch Community about the burning issues for businesses looking to drive business through innovating with data.

Around 60% of blogs will be from the wider Data Pitch community to ensure relevance to our audiences.

- **Company profiles and case studies** of both data providers and startups. What are they? What do they want to achieve? Why is Data Pitch so important to them?

Monitoring and tracking

Website

We have Google Analytics installed on the Data Pitch website, from this we are able to monitor:

- Site visits
- Page views
- Bounce rate
- Average time on site
- Pages per visit and percentage of new visits.

In addition to the data mentioned above, Google Analytics can also track referral traffic, including:

- Search engine
- Direct visits
- Website referrals
- Marketing campaigns (Pay Per Click, Banner advertising, e-mail marketing etc.)

Newsletter

We are using Mailchimp to manage our newsletter mailing list, and to create all newsletters. From this we can see how subscribers are growing and measure the following:

- Subscriber growth
- Open rates
- Click-through rates
- Forwarding of newsletters

Media reach

The Data Pitch communications team uses a proprietary service, showing reach for most UK media outlets and some European ones.

Twitter reach

From the Data Pitch Twitter account we can clearly see how many followers the account has and measure the following regularly:

- Follower growth
- Click-through rates
- Shares and likes - overall audience size
- Most successful tweets

Facebook Reach

On the Data Pitch Facebook account we are able to see an increase in page likes and measure the following:

- Follower growth

- Click-through rates - predominantly to the Data Pitch website
- Audience - based on shares and views

Marketing materials ([see Annex 5](#))

For Data Pitch's online presence, we have already created:

- [Project website](#)⁴ - including news stories and blogs, and a designed Data Pitch web banner
- Social media channels: [Twitter](#)⁵, [Facebook](#)⁶

The development of these channels is crucial for building the Data Pitch ecosystem and community over the coming three years.

For marketing, we have designed the following materials to be used at events and face to face meetings to give consistency and professionalism to the project:

- 2 Data Pitch logos, one long form, one short form, for use in appropriate channels.
- Two font series (Museo Sans and Calibri) which will be used through the documents about the Data Pitch project, such as the website, presentation slides, etc.
- Presentation templates - one branded blank template which can be used to create new presentations, and one corporate presentation with static graphics to be used to communicate the project to new audiences
- Stickers
- Roll-up exhibition banner
- Postcard flyer
- Brand guidelines

Development and delivery of communications workshops

The Data Pitch communications team will create template communication materials and 'how-to guide' to be used by startups to promote their own stories, in order to maximise economies of scale and upskill the startups themselves.

This will include:

- Press notice template and guide
- Guide to editorial formats and content - bylines, features, blogs, news stories etc
- Interview advice
- Social media guide

⁴ <https://datapitch.eu/>

⁵ <https://twitter.com/datapitcheu>

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/Data-Pitch-402275080131867/>

Summary

This dissemination, engagement and communication strategy is a flexible plan. Based on the defined target groups and objectives, the communication strategy aims to ensure that key audiences receive the full, lasting benefits of the Data Pitch programme.

Annexes

Annex 1: The Data Pitch Evaluation Goals

The following communications goals were set in the original grant agreement:

Participants in information campaign, webinars, peer networking events, hackathons	5K
Events attended by Data Pitch (invited talks, promotion of the call)	50
Size of community (incl. Twitter followers, mailing list subscribers, bloggers)	10K
Companies receiving information on the call	300K
Competitive call promotion reach	3M
Media coverage (editorials and clippings)	100
Press releases	10
Blog posts, tweets	3k

Annex 2: Events already attended on behalf on Data Pitch in 2017

Event	Date	Location
4YFN	28-30/2/2017	Barcelona
#DBhackathon	12-13/5/17	Berlin
Zoom Smart Cities	8/6/17	Lisbon
Mobility Business Hackathon	9-11/6/17	Berlin

Annex 3 Events Data Pitch plans to attend in 2017 (From 1st July 2017)

Event	Date	Location
TechDay London	27/8/2017	London
Slush	1/11-1/12/2017	Helsinki
Tech Open Air	12/07 - 14/07/2017	Berlin
Pirate Summit	6/9 - 7/9/2017	Cologne
London Food Tech Week	30/10 - 3/11/2017	London
Web Summit	6/11 - 9/11/2017	Lisbon
Noah Conference	2/11 - 3/11/2017	London

Annex 4 EU Countries and Horizon 2020 associated countries

EU countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

H2020 associated countries: Iceland, Norway, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, Israel, Moldova, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, Ukraine.

Annex 5 Marketing Assets

Please see visuals of some of the assets below, they are downloadable [here](#).

Data Pitch logos

Presentation templates

Opening slide:

Subsequent blank slides:

Example of slides with branded graphics to explain Data Pitch:

THE DATA PITCH ECOSYSTEM

Data innovators, entrepreneurs, enablers

Stickers

Brand guidelines

Data Pitch
Brand Rules

Colours

Our colours

Colours and their accurate reproduction are important to brand consistency.

<p>Data Pitch Dark Orange</p> <p>CMYK - 12/64/73/0 RGB - 204/102/102 HEX - #CC6666</p>	<p>Data Pitch Pale Yellow</p> <p>CMYK - 0/0/49/0 RGB - 255/255/153 HEX - #FFFF99</p>	<p>Data Pitch Yellow</p> <p>CMYK - 0/19/100/0 RGB - 255/204/0 HEX - #FFCC00</p>	<p>Data Pitch Orange</p> <p>CMYK - 0/48/88/0 RGB - 255/153/51 HEX - #FF9933</p>
<p>Data Pitch Pink</p> <p>CMYK - 17/92/0/0 RGB - 204/51/153 HEX - #CC3399</p>	<p>Data Pitch Dark Pink</p> <p>CMYK - 10/92/0/20 RGB - 204/51/102 HEX - #CC3366</p>	<p>Data Pitch Dark Red</p> <p>CMYK - 26/100/74/0 RGB - 153/0/51 HEX - #990033</p>	<p>Data Pitch Purple</p> <p>CMYK - 65/91/32/18 RGB - 102/51/102 HEX - #663366</p>
<p>Data Pitch Dark Teal</p> <p>CMYK - 90/42/55/22 RGB - 0/102/102 HEX - #006666</p>	<p>Data Pitch Teal</p> <p>CMYK - 77/21/42/0 RGB - 51/153/153 HEX - #339999</p>	<p>Data Pitch Dark Blue</p> <p>CMYK - 79/38/0/76 RGB - 0/47/79 HEX - #002F4F</p>	<p>Data Pitch Grey</p> <p>CMYK - 0/0/0/70 RGB - 102/102/102 HEX - #666666</p>

Data Pitch
Brand Rules

Typography

Our fonts

Our typeface is Museo Sans. It is a simple, modern sans-serif typeface allowing our communications to be clear and accessible.

Museo Sans 700

Aa

Museo Sans 300

Aa

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMm
NnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890!@£\$%^&*()--=